

RAW DATA			VALIDATION CHECKLIST				CONTEXT EXTRACTION		
group	participant ID	requirement	AGREED	FEASIBLE	NECESSARY	COMPLETE	traceability to the data-driven context model (numbered version)	list of CEs used in the requirement	number of CEs used in the requirement
control	p04	Give the user a hint saying "event already took place" when the "Event start date/time" was prior/is smaller than "Date/time"	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, event start date	2
control	p04	Give the user a hint saying something like "last comment is very old - post might be outdated" when "Date/time of last comment" is at least one month older than current "Date/time"	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, last comment time	2
control	p04	Cheer up the user if his/her comment had the "Content type" "Lament-feeling" by showing a funny image, like a cat image	yes	yes	no	n/a			
control	p04	Increase contrast or brightness of the application when "Part of the day" is "Evening" or "Dawn"	yes	yes	yes	yes		current part of the day	1
control	p04	If the post "Type" is "Offer" or "Seeking" and "Creation time" is older than 3 months (compared to "Date/time"), give the user a hint saying something like "The offer/seeking might be outdated"	yes	yes	yes	yes		post type, current time, post creation time	3
control	p04	If the "User" equals the "Author" of the post, ask the user if he/she wants to edit the original post or really post a comment.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current user, post author	2
control	p04	If the "User" is a "Suggestion worker" (Role) and the "Type" of the post is "Suggestion", ask the user if he/she wants to directly communicate with the author of the post.	yes	yes	yes	yes		post type, user role	2
control	p10	When creating a comment for a post of type OFFER, the system shall display the user predictive text, for typical questions, like: "How much?", "Is the object still available?"	yes	yes	yes	yes		post type	1
control	p10	When creating a comment a post of type SEEKING, the system shall display predictive text in form of greetings <<"good morning", "good afternoon", "good evening">> <<post_author>> based on the respective part of the day (morning, afternoon, or evening)	yes	yes	yes	yes		post type, current part of the day	2
control	p11	I as a user want to be informed when a new comment was made while writing a comment in order to have the ability update my comment with the latest discussion. Acceptance criteria: -The list of comments should be refreshed when I am writing a comment if a newer comment occurs -Before sending the comment the system is showing a popup prompting me if I have read the latest comments and still want to send my comment.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, last comment time	2
control	p11	I as a user want to have a hint if I am trying commenting on a post which is quite old. Acceptance criteria if the creation time is more than 15 days in the past or the last comment is older than 7 days and I am not the author of the post a small banner should be displayed above the comment field, that I am writing to a maybe outdated post.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, post creation time, last comment time, user, post author	5
control	p11	I as a user want to have a hint when commenting on a Suggestion that the local government might not reply when it is currently not in their office hours. Acceptance criteria: -The visual hint should be placed when the current time of the day is evening or dawn -the visual hint should be placed when the current day is a weekend	yes	yes	yes	yes		current part of the day, current day type	2
control	p11	I as a user want to be informed if an event already has started before commenting it.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, event start time	2
control	p12	When creating a comment on a suggestion at the weekend, the user should be automatically notified that the response might be given at the next workday.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current day type	1
control	p12	Information about author and creation time should be added to any comment.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
control	p12	User in the role suggestion worker should have predefined answers based on the content of the suggestion.	yes	no	n/a	n/a			
control	p12	The user should be able to select the content type when commenting an event.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
control	p12	The system should give a suggestion for content type when posting a comment on an event.	yes	yes	yes	no		content type	1
control	p12	The user should be notified when commenting on an event that has been in the past.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, event start time	2
control	p12	When creating a comment the user should be able to automatically like the given post.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
control	p12	The user should be able to display the user role when commenting.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
control	p13	The app orders the emojis by the content type of the comment. More concrete, if the content type is funny, the app provides emojis from the category funny.	yes	yes	yes	yes		content type	1
control	p13	The app automatically suggests the author of the post, when I type the first letter of his name.	yes	yes	yes	yes		user, post author	2
control	p13	The app automatically suggest the author of the post as first suggestions, when I type an "@".	yes	yes	yes	yes		user, post author	2
control	p13	If I logged in with account type Facebook, the app uses the post author to check whether we are already connected in Facebook. If we are not connected in Facebook, the app suggest to send a "add as friend" request via Facebook.	yes	yes	yes	yes		account type, user, post author	3
control	p13	If the date/time of last comment is newer then the time I started to write a comment, the app notifies me that there a new comments before submitting my comment.	yes	yes	yes	yes		last comment time, current time	2
control	p13	When I start writing a comment for event (news, etc.), the app presents me a graphical event (news, etc.) icon.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
control	p13	If I comment on an event post and the event is going to start within the next 30 minutes, the app notifies me that the event will start soon.	yes	yes	yes	yes		event start, current time	2

		When I comment on an event and the event start time happened more than three days in the past, the app notifies me that I write a comment for an already happened/finished event.	yes	yes	yes	yes	event start time, current time	2
control	p13	If user and post author are the same, the app notifies me that I am commenting my own post.	yes	yes	yes	yes	user, post author	2
control	p13	Depending on my role, the app suggests to add an icon in my post for admin, suggestions worker, ...	yes	yes	yes	yes	user role	1
control	p14	Automatically add the name of the user who is using the app in the salutation, e.g. "Best regards, Rodrigo!"	yes	yes	yes	yes	user	1
control	p14	Suggest comment text based on the user's role, e.g. "Thank you for your suggestion." for an employee of the administration.	yes	yes	yes	yes	user role	1
control	p14	Suggest a comment start text, depending on the time of day. E.g. "Good morning" if it is before 11 AM.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time	1
control	p14	Automatically suggest text "Sorry for replying late", if the date of the previous comment is longer than one day.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time, last comment time	2
control	p14	Suggest a salutation "Best regards, the administration of city ..." if the type of post is news. (because only city employees can post news.	yes	yes	yes	yes	post type	1
control	p14	Set the greeting depending on the part of the day, e.g. "Good morning", when it is morning.	yes	yes	yes	yes	part of the day	1
control	p14	Suggest emoticons depending on the Content type, e.g. 🙏 for Gratitude.	yes	yes	yes	yes	content type	1
control	p14	Warn user that an event is already over, when commenting on an event that has already happened, based on the Event start date/time.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time, event start date	2
control	p14	Show user that an event is about to happen soon, when Event start date/time is closer than 2h.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time, event start date	2
control	p14	Let people know, that they are likely to get an answer from administration on the next workday when Day type is Weekend, Type is Suggestion and Role is Normal.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current day type, post type, user role	3
control	p14	Suggest user to add a photo from the media library, when Type is suggestion.	yes	yes	yes	yes	post type	1
control	p14	Suggesting to share information about an event on facebook, when commenting on Type Event and Account type is FACEBOOK	yes	yes	yes	yes	post type, account type	2
control	p14	Automatically add greeting "Hi <Authors>" with the Post Author's name and Type Free talk	yes	yes	yes	yes	post type, post author	2
control	p14	Configuration to automatically include twitter handle in comments, when Account type is TWITTER	no	n/a	n/a	n/a	account type	1
control	p14	Automatically add link to Facebook profile, when Account type is FACEBOOK	no	n/a	n/a	n/a	account type	1
control	p14	Show a "hot" indicator, if the last like on a post was less than 5 minutes ago.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a	last like time	1
control	p14	Suggest to add a picture to the comment, if Type is Seeking	yes	yes	yes	yes	post type	1
control	p15	Depending on the role of the user, the background color of the comment should be adapted according to the following schema: admin = black suggestion worker = yellow DorfFunk support team = orange normal = white.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
control	p15	Depending on the "part of the day", a small icon is added to the comment visualizing the part of the day.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
control	p15	If the comment that is created is very close to the original comment, the system reacts to you. Concretely: An answer between 0 and 30 minutes after the original post shows a "fireworks" animation. An answer between 30 and 90 minutes shows "thumbs up" animation. Afterwards, no animation is shown.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time, post creation time	2
control	p15	Depending on the content type, the system suggests you some predefined answers you can use.	yes	yes	yes	yes	content type	1
control	p15	Depending on the content type, the system suggests you some predefined emoticons you can use.	yes	yes	yes	yes	content type	1
control	p15	When you write a comment and add a picture, you can choose whether to add the part of the day instead of the concrete timestamp.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
control	p15	if the type of comment is suggestion, and it is working day, the system reacts with a concrete number when a person from the municipality will react.	yes	yes	no	n/a		
treatment	p16	The system should suggest the author to post a reminder about the event and suggests content for the post, 10 hours before event starts.	yes	yes	yes	yes	User post author content type current time event start time	5
treatment	p16	The system suggests reactions (text blocks or emojis) to the post, when the user reads a new post.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
treatment	p16	The system should notify the user, when another user reacts on his/her post.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
treatment	p16	The system should ask the user to turn on the notification of dorf-funk, when the user is in the home-network after 17:00.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a		
treatment	p16	The system should remind the user to interact in the plausch-channel, when there is no new post in the channel in the last 24 hours.	yes	yes	no	n/a		
treatment	p16	The system should ask users that previously interact with the post with a "GRATITUDE or POSITIVE REACTION"-Comment to review the event.	yes	no	n/a	n/a	User comment author content type	3
treatment	p16	The system should notify the post-author about new post with content type "INTEREST" and "QUESTION".	yes	yes	yes	yes	User Post author Content type	3
treatment	p16	If there is no reaction in the post after 20hours, the system should suggest the autor to add a new comment.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time post creation time User Post author	4
treatment	p17	When the current time is between 1h15 after the event start time and 5h30m after event start time, the system shall send a notification to the user with a pre-defined comment template to show his/her gratitude.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time event start time content type	3
treatment	p17	When the current time is between 10h before event start and 2h before event start the system shall suggest a pre-defined reminder comment to a user who is the author.	yes	yes	yes	yes	current time event start time content type user	5

treatment	p17	When the current time is between 2 min after post creation time and 1h42 min after post creation time, the system shall send a notification to a user who is not the post author and ask whether he/she wants to provide a positive reaction.	yes	yes	no	n/a	4	current time post creation time user post author content type	5
treatment	p17	When a user is a post author, the system shall ask the him/her whether she/he wants to leave a comment and clarify something.	yes	yes	yes	yes	10	User post author content type	3
treatment	p17	When the current time is between 0 min after post creation time and 30 min after post creation time and it is afternoon, the system shall allow the users to leave a comment.	yes	yes	no	n/a	15	current time post creation time current part of the day	3
treatment	p17	When the current time is between 0 min after post creation time and 30 min after post creation time and post creation time was an afternoon or noon, the system shall allow the users to leave a comment.	yes	yes	no	n/a	16	current time post creation time post creation part of the day	3
treatment	p18	When the user is not a post author and the post is not older than 1 hour an 42 minutes the system offers the user the possibility to like the post.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a	4	user, post author, current time, post creation	4
treatment	p18	When the start time of an event is less than 10 hours and the user is the post author, then the system reminds the user to send a reminder for the event.	yes	yes	yes	yes	2	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p18	When the start time of an event is in 2 hours and the user is post author and has not sent a reminder, the system reminds the user to send a reminder for the event.	yes	yes	yes	yes	2	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p18	When the user is not post author and the post creation time has reached 1 minute, the system offers the user the possibility ask questions for a duration of one hour.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p18	If the time of the last comment to Plausch post exceeds 4 minutes, the system automatically deactivates the comment function for this Plausch post.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p18	As soon as the end time of an event exceeds one hour, the system activates the feedback function for the event for a duration of 13 hours.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p18	When the end time of an event exceeds 12 hours the system automatically sends a reminder that the user can provide feedback to the event for another 2 hours.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p18	The system only provides users that are not authors of an event with the possibility to post feedback to the event.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p18	When the creation time of a PLAUSCH post exceeds 20 minutes, the system disables the comment function.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p19	When the user is the author of a post about an event and the current time is between 10h and 2h before the event start time, the system shall remind the user to write a comment as a reminder to potential participants.	yes	yes	yes	yes	2	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p19	When a user attended an event of which they are not the author, and the current time is between 1h and 14h after the event started, the system shall remind the user to write a comment to praise the organizer.	yes	no	n/a	n/a	3		
treatment	p19	When a user reads a post that was created between 1 and 2h42 min ago, the system shall provide the user with the ability to like the post, indicate interest, and ask a question.	yes	yes	yes	yes		post creation date, current time, content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user reads a post that was created between 1 and 2h42 min ago, the system shall provide the user with the ability to like the post, indicate interest, and ask a question.	yes	yes	yes	yes		current time, post creation time, content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user is a post author and a question or opinion was received to that post, the system shall suggest the user to respond with a clarification.	yes	yes	yes	yes		user post author content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user views a post within 24 hours after the post was created, the system shall suggest the user to provide a helpful comment (e.g., motivational, opinion, funny).	yes	yes	yes	no	7	current time, post creation time, content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user views a post within 24 hours after the post was created, the system shall suggest the user to provide a helpful comment (e.g., motivational, opinion, funny).	yes	yes	yes	no	8	current time, post creation time, content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user views a post within 24 hours after the post was created, the system shall suggest the user to provide a helpful comment (e.g., motivational, opinion, funny).	yes	yes	yes	no	9	current time, post creation time, content type	3
treatment	p19	When a user reads a post on the weekend created that same weekend and the last comment was published at least 4 minutes ago, the system shall encourage the user to write a comment.	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p19	When a user opens their feed, the system shall automatically boost posts created less than 30 minutes ago.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p19	When the current time is between 2h before start time and 15 minutes after begin time of an event and the user is not the author of the event post, the system shall show the event in a section at the top of the user feed showing events starting soon.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p19	When a user has indicated interest for an event through a comment or by clicking an "Interested" button, and the event starts in less than 2 hours or has started less than 15 minutes ago, the system shall remind the user of the event.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			

treatment	p19	When an event starts in less than 2 hours or has started less than 15 minutes ago, the user is less than 2 km from the event site and the event matches the user's interest, the system shall recommend the event to the user.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p19	When a user is a post author and no comments were obtained from other users for 1 hour since the user last provided a clarification, the system shall encourage the author to provide further information, and will bump the post with other users if the user follows the suggestion by writing an additional post.	yes	yes	yes	yes	10	user, post author, last comment time, current time, content type	5
treatment	p20	10 hours before an event the system should send a reminder to the post author of the event asking them if they want to send a reminder for the event and suggest the text for the reminder	yes	yes	yes	yes	2	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p20	2 hrs after an event has occurred, the system should ask users that have provided comments on previous events if they would like to comment the occurred event	yes	no	n/a	n/a		current time, event start time	2
treatment	p20	If user is post author, the system should set the type of post to clarification when the user writes a new post for the same event, but allow the user to change it if necessary	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p20	The system should ask users if they want to send comments about an event only in the part of the day in which they have provided their most comments in the last 15 days	yes	no	n/a	n/a		current part of the day	1
treatment	p20	Before the event, if the user is not the author post, the system should provide automatic text / icon for giving a "positive reaction", showing "interest"	yes	yes	yes	yes	4	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p20	Before the event, if the user is not the author post, the system should provide automatic text / icon for giving a "positive reaction", showing "interest"	yes	yes	yes	yes	5	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p20	Before the event, if the user is not the author post, the system should provide set of common questions related to events and allow the user to select one or more of them	yes	yes	yes	yes	6	current time, event start time, user, post author, content type	5
treatment	p21	Automate contenttype during event: if a user wants to create a comment for an event after it started and ran for a while (1h15 to 5h30), automatically preset contenttype to "GRATITUDE" in the app and show this to the user	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p21	automate contenttype: if the post author for an event wants to create a comment on the event ahead of the event (10h to 2h), automatically preset the contenttype to "REMINDER" and make this visible to the user before posting	yes	yes	no	n/a			
treatment	p21	ability to comment 1: users must be able to comment on posts or other comments independently of day or daytime.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p21	ability to comment 2: users must be able to comment on posts or other comments independently of their role.	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p21	contenttype recommendation: if a user who is author of a post wants to create a comment on this post, then recommend "CLARIFICATION" as contenttype to the user	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			
treatment	p21	contenttype recommendation: if a user who is not author of a post for an event wants to create a comment on this post after the event has started (1h - 14h), then recommend "PRAISE" as contenttype to the user	no	n/a	n/a	n/a			